

LOW COST ADVANCED COMPOSITES (HIGH SPEED PATROL BOATS)

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ABSTRACT

In 1991, our Company, Bazán, developed a low cost, light structure for a high speed patrol boat.

The following materials were used: Matrixes, vinylester resin and polyester resin for inner modules (non structural). Fibers, multiaxial fabrics of E-glass. Cores, PVC foam in several densities as a structural core, including linear foam as resilient core.

The wet lay-up method is used for the main pieces (hull, deck and inner structure) and the wet-preg method for secondary bonding. To bond the core, vacuum bagging techniques are used.

Keywords: patrol boats, fast light crafts, boatbuilding, GRP

1. INTRODUCTION

Bazan, started a project in 1991 to develop a low cost, light structure for a fast patrol boat. For this reason a prototype was built in a plain single skin marine GRP, i.e. using polyester resin and heavy E-glass woven roving. This prototype underwent sea trials and evaluation tests for more than three months; structure and forms were optimized and consequently some changes were introduced in the former structure and propulsion system. The design and construction was to be surveyed by a Clasification Society as well as by our Quality Management department. A Workshop Manual was produced among our Technical, Production and Quality Management departments covering all important areas: structure, propulsion system and services. This Manual was intended to have a 'built-in' Quality Assurance method specially developed in the composites aspect, being this the most difficult area to cover.

2. MATERIAL SELECTION

2.1. Matrixes

The most common choice of a matrix for marine use is orthophthalic polyester protected by an isophthalic gel-coat or epoxy paint. The use of isophthalic resin for laminating can be considered a step beyond because of its salt water resistance and better mechanical properties, but its elongation at break is only somewhat higher. Vinylester resins have several good properties for the marine use. First of all is its excellent chemical resistance in a salt water environment. A no less important point is its mechanical properties, but the most outstanding for us is the high elongation at break (5%), since we are dealing with a structure subject to very frequent impact loads.

For the inner accommodation modules we chose an orthophthalic polyester resin since these modules are non structural and no special requirements were made concerning fire protection. The choice of phenolic resin is not advisable in a small craft for marine use because of its high water absorbance and its higher manufacturing cost.

2.2. Fibers

E-glass is the best choice for fiber type. First of all its low cost. Modulus is not so important in this type of vessels and because it is built in sandwich it is not so difficult to obtain the necessary stiffness playing with the core thickness. Strength to weight ratio is good enough.

We specified heavy multiaxial cloth for the main laminates combined with a double bias cloth (biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$) for stiffeners. As the stiffeners were designed with a unidirectional tape on top of them, we talked to our weaver and had them stitched to the central part of the double bias tape for the top hat stiffeners, so that when laid, the webs were made of double bias fabric and the flange of double bias and unidirectional tape in one shot, reducing manufacturing time.

We have also used chopped strand mat to prevent the fiber pattern through the gel coat and woven roving for minor pieces.

2.3. Cores

The core selection can be made among balsa wood, honeycomb and PVC foam. The first two can absorb a great amount of water in case of damage, resulting in a very wide area to repair. This should be considered when designing a heavy duty structure sailing at 40 plus knots. PVC foams have several good properties when designing marine structures. It has close cells, so water absorbance is kept to a minimum. You can choose among a wide variety of densities so you can make the best compromise between cost/weight and mechanical performances. Its specific strength is higher than balsa wood. There is also a special grade called linear or resilient that can undergo extreme strains and resist very heavy impacts. Other important advantage is its very good thermal and acoustical isolation. The main problem of PVC foam is its incapability to resist moderate temperatures but such temperatures are not normal in this type of vessels. This is a point that has to be taken into consideration when choosing the adhesive system so that not to damage the foam due to the

exothermal peak.

The choice was the following:

- linear foam in the bottom because is the part subject to impact loads.
- rigid foam in the topsides and bulkheads because these parts are not so loaded and its mechanical properties and cost are better.
- high density foam in highly shear or compression stressed areas.

We have also used poliurethane foam as ineffective core for stiffeners and saturated polyester fiber mat for several minor pieces as inner doors, hatches, covers, linings ..., to reduce weight for a given stiffness.

3. PROCESSES

Tooling consists mainly of a hull mould, a deck-lower superstructure mould and an upper superstructure mould. All the moulds are FRP female moulds taken from a wood model. This method is good when building medium to large series because reduces greatly the fairing, finishing and painting of the unit and you can even use gel-coat and have no finishing at all.

The wet lay-up method is used for the main pieces (hull, deck and inner structure) and the wet-preg method for secondary bonding, getting a better control over the resin content and being cleaner to use also.

To bond the core, vacuum bagging techniques are used, thus eliminating air pockets and improving properties, specially impact and fatigue. The vac-bag we used is a very simple one and is a non-bleeding bag, used only for consolidation.

The core bedding material chosen was a filled vinylester resin developed by us. The fillers were basically a light hollow sphere filler to lower the density and a thixotropic filler. We think this a better alternative for core bonding than the other methods explained in ref. 1, taking into account that we have used an even better resin and we used vac-bag techniques.

The problem we found when using vinylesters is that it runs easily, so we had two ways to go; one was filling the resin with a thixotropic agent and the other was reducing the gel-time. It is not advisable to use the thixotroper since it would be very hard to impregnate the heavy cloths we used, so we decided to bring the gel-time down a little.

4. TESTS AND QUALITY ASSURANCE

A series of tests were carried out to check and optimize mechanical properties. These test panels were laminated under workshop conditions. The tests were the following:

Tensile test according to ISO 3268-1978, flexural test (three points) according to ISO 178-1975 and shear test for sandwich panels according to ASTM C 273-61. Besides, we checked the resin to fiber ratio according to ASTM D 2584-68 (1985).

All the results exceeded the expected, specially resin to fiber ratio values, where we got 60% fiber content by weight.

For Quality Assurance we produced a Workshop Manual. This Manual was intended to be a self contained quality system for the construction of the crafts, specially in the composites part. This manual monitored the reception of materials, storage, gel-coat layer, mixing of laminating resin, lay-up process, mixing of adhesive and core-bonding process as well as the environmental conditions, temperature and moisture.

The construction was surveyed by a Classification Society and the design and quality system were approved by them. The Factory where the crafts were built have a PECAL-4 Qualification, that is the Spanish version of NATO AQAP-4 Standard.

5. CONCLUSIONS AND FURTHER WORK

It is possible to obtain a reasonably light structure at reasonable cost, i.e. not using carbon/epoxy composites. Future work can go in several directions. Let us analyze them briefly.

5.1. Matrixes

Elongation at break still remains a major concern, so, any work should go in this direction. Besides this, we should keep in mind the cost, being a clear point in this paper, so we could use in a future improved vinylesters or the new vinylester-urethanes and similar resin systems.

5.2. Reinforcements

More work can be done with thinner fabrics in order to get a sharper control of the resin content and optimizing the weight per surface area.

5.3. Cores

The most important area to improve is the core bonding system, trying to get a low cost and flexible adhesive with low exothermal peak. Maybe the way to go is using polyester mat for the reasons explained in ref. 1 and 2.

5.4. Processes

Using an airless spraying-gun lay-up time is shortened. The other improvement we are developing now is using a resin injection/transfer process to reduce styrene emission, to get a better control over the resin to fiber ratio and hence improve weight/structural performances.

6. REFERENCES

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RELIABILITY

